

SMARANDACHE ROUTE SEQUENCES

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Consider a rectangular city with a mesh of tracks which are of equal length and which are either horizontal or vertical and meeting at nodes. If one row contains m tracks and one column contains n tracks then there are $(m+1)(n+1)$ nodes. To begin with let the city be of a square shape i.e. $m = n$.

Consider the possible number of routes R which a person at one end of the city can take from a source S (starting point) to reach the diagonally opposite end D the destination.

(m rows and m columns)

Refer Figure -I

For $m = 1$ Number of routes $R = 1$

For $m = 2$, $R = 2$

For $m = 3$, $R = 12$

We see that for the shortest routes one has to travel $2m$ units of track length. There are routes with $2m + 2$ units up to the longest route being $4m + 4$.

We define **Smarandache Route Sequence (SRS)** as the number of all possible routes for a ' m ' square city. This includes routes with path lengths ranging from $2m$ to $4m + 4$.

Open problem(1): To derive a reduction formula/ general formula for SRS.

Here we derive a reduction formula, thus a general formula for the number of **shortest routes**.

Reduction formula for number of shortest routes:

Refer figure -II

Let $R_{j,k}$ = number of routes to reach node (j, k) .

Node (j , k). Can be reached only either from node (j-1, k) or from the node (j , k-1) . * {As only shortest routes are to be considered }.

It is clear that there is only one way of reaching node (j , k) from node (j-1 , k). Similarly there is only one way of reaching node (j , k) from node (j , k-1). Hence the number of shortest routes to node (j , k) is given by

$$R_{j,k} = 1. R_{j-1,k} + 1. R_{j,k-1} = R_{j-1,k} + R_{j,k-1}$$

This gives the reduction formula for $R_{j,k}$.

Applying this reduction formula to fill the chart we observe that the total number of shortest routes to the destination (the other end of the diagonal) is ${}^{2n}C_n$. This can be established by induction .

We can further categorize the routes by the number of **turning points** it is subjected to.

The chart for various number of turning points(TPs) for a city with 9 nodes is given below.

No of TPs	1	2	3	4
No of routes	2	2	2	5

Further Scope:

(1) To explore for patterns among total number of routes , number of turning points and develop formulae for square as well as rectangular meshes (cities).

(2) To study as to how many routes pass through a given number/set of nodes? How many of them pass through all the nodes?

Figure-I

